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Monetary Policy Instruments And Economic Growth In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research work examined the impact of monetary policy instruments on economic growth in Nigeria within the period of 1981 to 2022. Data was sourced from CBN statistical bulletin. Gross domestic product (GDP) was used as proxy for economic growth while the independent variables were interest rate (ITR), exchange rate (EXR), Open market operation proxied by treasury bill rate (TBR), reserve requirement ratio (RRR) and inflation rate (INF) used as controlled variable. Consequently, this research work adopted Ex-Post Factor research design in which multiple regression method of analysis was used. Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF), Philip Perron (PP), Zivot-Andrews (ZA) and Dynamic ARDL were employed as the research techniques, specifically for unit root tests and estimation of the long run and short run relationship of the variable. The results showed that: interest rate has negative and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria by contributing to 0.0087% and 0.009% decrease in GDP in short and long run periods respectively. However, Open market operation proxied by treasury bill rate has positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria by contributing to 0.012% and 0.43% increase in GDP in short and long run periods respectively. On the contrary, reserve requirement ratio negatively and insignificantly impacted on economic growth by leading to 0.07% and 0.03% decrease in GDP in the short and long run periods respectively. Similarly, exchange rate has negative and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria by contributing to 0.094% and 0.093% decrease in GDP in both the short and long run periods respectively. Lastly, inflation rate has negative and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria by contributing to 0.003% and 0.002% decrease in GDP in the short and long run periods respectively. Based on the results, this work recommends that government should liberalize interest rate such that will reduce prime lending rate and thereby encourage investors to access the credit available for domestic investment in Nigeria. Again, government should embark on policies that would increase the commercial bank reserve as that would increase the availability of funds to the investor for investment and in turn promote private domestic investment

Keywords:

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The achievement of macroeconomic goals such as full employment, stability of price level, high and sustainable economic growth, has been a policy priority of every economy. The realization of these goals is not automatic, but requires policy guidance, and this policy guidance represents the objective of economic policy (Atuma & Eze, 2017). The formulation and proper implementation of these appropriate macroeconomic policies and programmes-targeted for economic growth, along with improved access to social services and infrastructures, are essential ingredients in any strategy for poverty alleviation, especially in developing countries. Such macroeconomic policies that could be used to actualize the above mentioned goals, involve the deliberate manipulation of policy instruments. One of such policies is monetary policy and its major variables are open market operations (OMOs), interest rate, cash reserve requirement, discount rate, liquidity ratio, selective credit control, moral suasion, among others; and the effectiveness of any instrument depends on certain basic market and administrative attributes (Atuma & Eze, 2017).

Overtime, the role of policy instruments in economic activities and stabilization of economies among countries of the world has remained a subject of major debate between the monetarists and the Keynesians School of thoughts. The monetarists argued that economic activities of countries are greatly influenced by the monetary policy instruments, while the Keynesians countered the argument by maintaining that the economic activities of countries are more influenced by fiscal policy instruments. To buttress this point, the monetarists were of the opinion that changes in money supply affects output level and economic growth of a nation. That is, for the level of output and economic growth to increase, the monetarists argued that the monetary authorities should increase the level of money stock in the economy. (Awogbemi, 2022).

Low interest rate give rise to increased access to credit facilities which increases employment of factors of production and through the multiplier, it raises output, income and employment. Reserve requirement influences banks ability to give out loans that eventually facilitate investment activities and eventual increase in output, employment, exports and reduction in poverty. Reduction in reserve requirement ratio especially in periods of recession enable banks play its role as financial intermediation which helps to stimulate the growth of an economy and enhance the financial development of a country. Discounting treasury bills rate helps in various ways in financing government budget deficit through internal borrowing. Changes in exchange rate have powerful effect of relative prices of goods and services (Ibrahm and Enofe, 2021)

Prior to 1986, the financial environment in Nigeria was identified by the desire for growth in the oil sector, the increasing role of the public sector and the external sector over dependence. In order to maintain price stability and healthy balance of payments position, monetary management before 1986 depended on the use of direct instruments such as credit ceilings, selective credit controls or credit rationing, administered rate of interest and the recommendation of cash reserve requirements and special deposits (Udochukwu, 2021).

From the mid 1970s, according to Udochukwu (2021), achieving monetary policy objectives became difficult. It was observed that banks aggregate loans to the productive sectors between 1972 and 1985, average 40.7% to total credit, about 8.7% points lower than the stipulated target of 49.4%. At that time, all parameters of economic growth tended southwards. Such parameters are fiscal deficits, monetary aggregates, GDP growth rate, inflation rate and balance of payments. The compliance of banks to credit guidelines was below average. The strategy of credit ceiling and selective credit controls by CBN failed and never achieved its objective. Based on the controlled interest rate regime, expansion of the monetary system was encouraged, without the expected growth in the money and capital markets respectively. The interest rate introduced at that time by government on debts of government which was low, never achieved the attraction of savers from the private sector. In the early 1980s, the borrowings of government from the CBN as a result of not having enough revenue from the oil sector which happens to be where government depended solely to finance budgets caused so much adverse effect on the management of the monetary system. In line with the economic deregulation embodied in the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), there was a paradigm shift from the hitherto repressive direct monetary control method to an indirect approach which was to use market instruments in monetary management. This came up in order to eradicate the administrative

bottlenecks and inefficiencies in the financial system so as to encourage competition in the banking subsector in particular and in the financial sector in general. Between 1986-2001, money supplied to the economy was more than the target for the period with wide margin. Hence, the inflation rate in 1999 fell to 6.62% from 9.98% it was in 1998. In 2000 it was 6.94% while in 2001 it skyrocketed to 18.03%, aggregate output was sluggish during the period. (CBN, 2021)

During the monetary policy implementation Post-Consolidation (2006-2007), the monetary policy rate (MPR) was also used by the CBN as a nominal anchor to influence the level and direction of other interest rates. The changes indicated whether the monetary authorities wished to adopt a policy of monetary tightening or otherwise (Udochukwu, 2021).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The major goals of implementing monetary policy include to achieve sustainable economic growth, exchange rate stability, price stability, financial sector stability, balance of payments equilibrium and full employment. However, despite the various monetary policy instruments adopted by government through its agencies (CBN) to achieve macroeconomic goals of the nation, price instability, unsustainable economic growth, disequilibrium of balance of payments, high rate of unemployment, exchange rate and financial sector instabilities still remain the major threat to Nigeria's international trade as well as other macroeconomic activities in the economy (Balogun, 2007; Atuma & Eze2017; Udochukwu, 2021). For example, the high unemployment trend in Nigeria reveals that it has increased astronomically from 3.5 percent in 1980 to 4.3 percent in 1985. From 2006 until 2020, the unemployment rate in Nigeria averaged 13.55 percent, reaching an all-time high of 33.30 percent in the fourth quarter of 2020 and a record low of 5.10 percent in the fourth quarter of 2010. In 2022, the unemployment rate in Nigeria was 33 percent, a figure that was projected to be 32.5 percent in the preceding year (NBS, 2023). According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023), Nigeria's unemployment rate increased in the third quarter (Q3) of 2023 to 5.0 percent. This represents an increase of 0.8 percent compared to the 4.2 percent recorded in Q2 2023. Chronological data show that the unemployment rate in Nigeria has increased constantly in the past few years (NBS, 2023).

Considering the trend of gross domestic product, interest rate, exchange rate, reserve requirement ratio and Open market operation for five (5) years interval, it was observed that in 1981, gross domestic product was -13.1%, interest rate was 5%, exchange rate was 0.62%, and Open market operation was 5%. In 1986, gross domestic product increased to 0.1%, interest rate increased to 10%, exchange rate increased to 1.75%, and Open market operation increased to 8.50%. This implies that the increase in monetary policy in Nigeria does not bring a corresponding increase in economic growth in the country. Similar effect was observed in 1991 when gross domestic product increased to 0.4%, interest rate increased to 18.5%, exchange rate increased to 9.91%, and Open market operation increased to 15%. In 1996 gross domestic product increased to 5.9%, interest rate decreased to 13.5%, exchange rate increased to 21.9%, reserve requirement ratio was 16.95% and Open market operation decreased to 12.25%. In 2001, gross domestic product increased to 5.9%, interest rate remained 13.5%, exchange rate decreased to 111.7%, reserve requirement ratio increased to 125.26% and Open market operation increased to 12.95%. In 2006, gross domestic product increased to 6.1%, interest rate decreased to 13%, exchange rate increased to 128.65%, reserve requirement ratio increased to 206.51 % of deposit and Open market operation decreased to 8.80%. In the year 2011, gross domestic product decreased to 5.3% of GDP, interest rate decreased to 6.13% of principal, exchange rate increased to 153%, reserve requirement ratio increased to 770.05 % of deposit and Open market operation increased to 16.75%. In the year 2016, gross domestic product decreased to 1.6%, interest rate increased to 13.6% of principal, exchange rate decreased to 97.27%, Open market operation increased 18.50%. Finally in the year 2021, gross domestic product increased to 3.6%, interest rate decreased to 5% of principal, exchange rate decreased to 43.58% of GDP and Open market operation decreased to 10% (CBN, 2021).

It is expected, forexample, that low interest rate due to availability of money in an economy should lead to the growth of the domestic investment vis-a-vis economic growth. But after observing the trend of gross domestic product, it is observed that there is contradiction in relation to the theory as increase or decrease in monetary policy instruments do not lead to proportionate increase or decrease in gross domestic product in Nigeria. The adverse economic implication of such deviations in the country's economic activities are the periodic increase in the country's unemployment and inflation

rate to as high as 5.76% and 18.8% in 2022 respectively; as well as the external sector disequilibria; and these factors are highly conjectured as being able to militate against the growth of any economy. It is against this background that the researcher wishes to examine the significant empirical impact of monetary policy instruments on economic growth in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions are raised so as to provide answers to the research problem.

- 1 To what extent has interest rate impacted on economic growth in Nigeria?
- 2 To what magnitude has exchange rate impacted on economic growth in Nigeria?
- 3 How has open market operation impacted on economic growth in Nigeria?
- 4 To what extent has reserve requirement ratio impacted on economic growth in Nigeria?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to empirically investigate the impact of monetary policy instruments on economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives are to:

- 1 determine the extent at which interest rate impact on economic growth in Nigeria
2. evaluate the magnitude at which exchange rate impacts on economic growth in Nigeria
3. ascertain if open market operation significantly impacts on economic growth in Nigeria
- 4 determine the extent at which reserve requirement ratio impacts economic growth in Nigeria

1.5 Hypotheses of the Study

The following null hypotheses are formulated to guide the study:

- 1 There is no significant impact between interest rate and economic growth in Nigeria.
- 2 There is no significant impact between exchange rate and economic growth in Nigeria.
- 3 Open market operation has no significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.
- 4 Reserve requirement ratio has no significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study will be beneficial to individuals', government or policy makers and also the future researchers in the following ways: Individuals have information as regard the impact of monetary policy instruments on economic growth and how it can contribute to the development of Nigeria productive capacity. The government and policy makers would spot the importance of monetary policy instruments on the economic growth and encourage policies that would ensure that domestic investment is promoted to contribute to the growth of national output in Nigeria. The findings and recommendations of this work will provide literature for further researchers.

1.7 Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study investigated the impact of monetary policy instruments on economic growth using Nigeria as a case study. The period for this study is from 1981 to 2022. The variables of interest for this study are gross domestic product (GDP), interest rate (ITR), exchange rate (EXR), Open market operation proxied by Treasury Bill Rate (TBR), and Reserve Requirement Ratio (RRR).

The study is limited by difficulties in accessing reliable and large data due to the fact that there are many inconsistent of data from different sources but; the researcher made serious effort to source reliable data from reliable source.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 The Classical Monetary Theory

The quantity theory of money underpins the classical economist view of monetary policy. The quantity theory of money is typically discussed in terms of the fisherman equation of exchange, denoted by the expression, $MV = PT$. M denotes the supply of money over which the federal government has some control, V denotes the velocity of circulation of money which is the average number of times a currency is spent on final goods and service in a year, P denotes the GDP price level, and T denotes volume of transactions. The theory assumes that V and T are constant in the short run. Given that V and T are both fixed, it follows that if the central bank of Nigeria (CBN) engages in expansionary (or contractionary) monetary policy, it will result in an increase (or decrease) in money supply (M) with the only effect being an increase (or decrease) in price level P in direct proportion to the change in money supply (M). The equation of exchange is an identity which states that the current

market value of all final goods and services (nominal GDP) must equal the supply of money multiplied by the average number of times a currency is used in transaction in a given year.

2.1.2 Monetarist Theory of Monetary Policy

Milton Friedman founded the monetarist school of thought. They created a more stable version of the quantity theory of money. They established that money supply is the key factor affecting the well-being of the economy and accepted the need for an effective monetary policy to stabilize an economy, they also believe that in order to promote consistent growth, the money supply should grow at a fixed rate rather than being regulated and altered by monetary authorities (Awogbemi, 2022). Thus, monetarists argue that in the short-run, expansionary monetary policy may raise the level of GDP by increasing aggregate demand.

2.1.3 Keynesian Monetary Theory

Keynesian theory rejected the idea that money and price have a direct and proportional relationship. They all agree that it is done indirectly through interest rate. That also rejected the notion that the economy is always at or near its national level of real GDP, implying that T in the equation of exchange is fixed. They also reject the idea that the velocity of money in circulation is constant. Keynesians believes that increasing the supply of loanable funds available through the banking system, interest rates will fall. When interest rate fall, aggregate expenditure in investment and interest-sensitive consumer goods rise, causing real GDP to rise. As a result, monetary policy can have an indirect impact on real GDP. The theory suggests that in the short run, monetary policy can affect real economic variables such as output and employment through its impact on nominal variables like interest rates and inflation (Awogbemi, 2022).

2.1.4 Romer Model of Endogenous Growth Theory

The key idea behind Romer-model of endogenous growth theory is that certain variables within and economy, including innovation and institutions, can be actively influenced and nurtured to promote economic growth. Endogenous growth, therefore emphasizes the role of institution in driving long term economic growth. The theory suggests that strong institutions, including efficient governance structures, create a conducive environment for investment, innovation and entrepreneurship. Institutions that provide stability, promote fair competition, and protect intellectual property rights, encourage long-term economic growth. Thus, this theory supports the view that once prudent monetary policy decisions are made in the presence of quality institutions characterized by efficient legal systems and better governance structures, economic growth is evident, *ceteris paribus* (Awogbemi, 2022)

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

Awogbemi (2022) examined the impact of monetary policy on Nigeria's economic growth, using descriptive statics and the ordinary least squares method. The result revealed that liquidity ratio has a negative impact on the Nigerian economy while money supply variable had a positive and significant impact on Nigerian economic growth over time.

Ibrahim & Enofe (2021) investigated the relationship between monetary policy instruments and economic growth in Nigeria, using auto –regressive distributed lag (ARDL) method. The results revealed that only interest rate and broad money had a positive and significant impact on economic growth in the country.

Ovat, Ishaku, Ugbaka & Ifere (2022) evaluated the effect of monetary policy rate on Nigeria's economic growth using OLS. The findings revealed that monetary policy rate has a negative but significant effect on economic growth, real exchange rate has an inverse relationship and significant effect on economic growth.

Ajisafe, Adesini & Okunade (2022) investigated the impact of monetary policy instruments on output in Nigeria. Their findings using VECM indicated that there is a long-run relationship between expected and unexpected monetary policy and output in Nigeria.

Okoh & Otene (2020) examined the impact of monetary policy on inflation and economic growth in Nigeria using the vector Auto-regression Technique (VAR) and found that money supply has a positive impact on economic growth,

Other studies with conflicting impact of monetary policy instrumentson economic growth and development of a country include Hassaini, Gylych, Abdurahman & Murat (2020), Atuma & Eze (2017), Oluseyi,, John & Udoye (2018), Ezeaku, Ibe, Igwuanyi, Modebe & Agbaeze (2018), Tude,

Ogundele & Apinran (2018), Ufoeze, Odimgbe, Ezeabalisi & Alajekwu (2018), Saghir, Hadiqa, & Syed (2022), Khaysy, Thiphavanh, Vaiyoth, Phiengsanith, Visanu, & Vonsy (2021), Oyakegha & Arepo (2022), Nwankwor, Ikeora, & Ogini (2022), Timothy (2022), etc. The conflicting results can be attributed to differences in methodological approach, scope, or dataset.

2.4 Gap in Empirical Literature

Gap in empirical literature implies the missing constituent. From the empirical studies reviewed, all the study reviewed adopted the ARDL method and other econometrics methods like ordinary least square (OLS), vector error correction model (VECM), vector autoregressive technique (VAR) etc to carry out their investigation, eg, Ibrahim & Enofe (2021), Saghir, Hadiqa & Syed (2022), Timothy (2022), Gideon, Gylych, Paul, Bilal & Onyinye (2020) Atuma & Eze (2017), Abille & Mpuure (2020), etc, used the ARDL econometrics method. This study adopted the Dynamic Autoregressive Distributed Lag (DARDL) simulation. The novel dynamic ARDL simulations algorithm is useful for testing co-integration, long and short run equilibrium relationships in both levels and differences. Thus, the dynamic ARDL simulations and Kernel-based Regularized Least Squares techniques are useful and improved time series techniques for policy formulation, compared to the ARDL and other econometrics methods that were used by other researchers reviewed in this study. Secondly, the period covered by this study (1981-2022) is more recent and addresses more current issues that borders on this area of study, compared to previous researchers investigations reviewed in this study.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Method

This research work employs multiple regression method in which dynamic autoregressive distributed lag model (DARDL) technique is used as a method of analysis to determine the relationships between gross domestic product (GDP) known as the dependent variable and interest rate (INT), exchange rate (EXR), Open market operation proxied by (Treasury bills rate), and reserve requirement ratio (RESR) known as independent variables.

3.2 Model Specification

The theoretical framework of this model will be anchored on Romer Model of Endogenous growth theory. This theory is expressed in the form of Cobb- Douglas production functions:

$$Y = AK^\alpha L^{1-\alpha} \tag{1}$$

Where: Y = total production in any economy, A = total factor productivity, K = capital, L = labour, and the parameter α measures the output elasticity of capital. Hence, in order to achieve the objectives of this study, our model is therefore stated as thus:

$$GDP = f(ITR, EXR, TBR, RRR, INF) \tag{2}$$

Equation two (2) above will be modified and state econometrically as

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ITR_{t-1} + \beta_2 EXR_{t-1} + \beta_3 TBR_{t-1} + \beta_4 RRR_{t-1} + \beta_5 INF_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \tag{3}$$

Where GDP = Gross Domestic Product, ITR= interest rate, EXR= exchange rate as, TBR= Treasury bills rate, and RRR =reserve requirement ratio, INF = inflation, $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ are regression coefficients of both dependent and independent variables specified and ϵ_t = Error Term.

3.3 DATA DISCUSSION

i). Gross Domestic Product (GDP):

This is the total monetary value of goods and services produced within a country usually a year. With this, the standard of living of the populace in the country can be determined. It is concerned with domestic production and does not, include net income from abroad.

ii). Interest Rate: This is the percentage of the principal amount, charged by the lender or bank to the borrower for the use of its assets or money for a specific time period. The rate a bank pays to its depositors for keeping money in a savings account, recurring deposit, or fixed deposit is also termed as the interest rate.

iii). Treasury Bill Rate: This is a short-term government debt security with a maturity of less than one year. Unlike many other debt securities that make regular interest payments to investors, Treasury bills yield no interest. Rather, the bills are sold at a discount to their redemption price.

iv). **Reserve Requirement Ratio:** This refers to the portion of total deposits that the commercial banks are obligated to maintain with the central bank in cash reserve, and it will not be available for any commercial lending. It is derived by dividing the cash reserve maintained with the central bank by the bank deposits.

3.4 Sources of Data

The researcher sourced the data from the relevant central bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin of the current year and World Bank data on Nigeria.

3.5 Estimation Procedure

The time series properties of data were examined in order to avoid spurious result emanating from the non stationarity of the data and to analyze the dynamic structure of the relationship. The estimation begins with a unit root test to confirm the stationarity state of the variables that enter the model using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF), Philip Perron and Zivot-Andrews (ZA). Consequently, conducting the tests with and devoid of a deterministic trend (t) for all the series and comparing P-Values with the critical values at 5% significance level, we observed that the series have mixed order of integration, Auto-regressive distributed lag (ARDL) model will be applied

Dynamic Autoregressive Distributed Lag (DARDL) Simulation Model

The application of the dynamic ARDL simulation model was due to the complexity in interpreting ARDL models with initial differences and lagged differences. As interpreting both the long-run and short-run implications of changes in the independent variables become more difficult, Jordan and Philips (2018) developed dynamic simulated ARDL model to simulate a number of ARDL models to overcome the interpretation hinges. The ARDL model in general is as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \theta_0 y_{t-1} + \theta_1 x_{1,t-1} + \dots + \theta_k x_{k,t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_1} \beta_{1j} \Delta x_{1,t-j} + \dots + \sum_{j=0}^{q_k} \beta_{kj} \Delta x_{k,t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Two of the most restrictions are the ARDL(1,1) model with all-stationary data is below:

$$y_t = \alpha_0 + \varphi_1 y_{t-1} + \theta_{1,0} x_{1,t} + \dots + \theta_{k,0} x_{k,t} + \theta_{1,1} x_{1,t-1} + \dots + \theta_{k,1} x_{k,t-1} + e_t \quad 8$$

This target estimating the non-stationary and cointegrating variant, usually referred to as error correction model and the model is as follows:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha_0 + \varphi_1 y_{t-1} + \theta_{1,1} x_{1,t-1} + \dots + \theta_{k,1} x_{k,t-1} + \beta_1 \Delta x_{1,t} + \dots + \beta_k \Delta x_{k,t} + e_t \quad 9$$

Equation 12 reveals the first difference of the dependent variable y_t at time $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ as a function of an intercept (α_0), the first lag of the regressed in levels (y_{t-1}), the first lag of regressors in levels, $x_{1,t-1}, x_{2,t-1}, \dots, x_{k,t-1}$, and up to maximum lags p and $q_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, of the first differences of dependent and independent variables, with an error term e_t .

RESULTS

4.1 Unit Root Test

In order to test for the presence or absence of unit root in the data used for the empirical analysis, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), Philip Perron (PP) and Zivot-Andrews (ZA) unit root tests were employed and the test results are as presented below:

Table 1: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test Results

Variables	Level			First Difference			Remarks
	t-Statistics	5% critical value	p-value	t-statistics	5%-critical value	p-value	
LGDP	-1.455	-2.955	0.5557	-3.500	-2.958	0.0080	I(1)
ITR	-2.767	-2.955	0.0632	-7.340	-2.958	0.0000	I(1)
TBR	-3.489	-2.955	0.0083	-----	-----	-----	I(0)
LRRR	-0.378	-2.955	0.9137	-5.202	-2.958	0.0000	I(1)
LEXR	-2.052	-2.955	0.2641	-5.470	-2.958	0.0000	I(1)
INF	-3.050	-2.955	0.0304	-----	-----	-----	I(0)

Table 2: Philips-Perron Unit Root Test Results

Variables	Level			First Difference			Remarks
	t-Statistics	5% critical value	p-value	t-statistics	5%-critical value	p-value	
LGDP	-1.111	-2.955	0.7107	-3.469	-2.958	0.0088	I(1)
ITR	-2.704	-2.955	0.0734	-7.476	-2.958	0.0000	I(1)
TBR	-3.448	-2.955	0.0094	-----	-----	-----	I(0)
LRRR	-0.452	-2.955	0.9010	-5.203	-2.958	0.0000	I(1)
LEXR	-2.101	-2.955	0.2441	-5.458	-2.958	0.0000	I(1)
INF	-3.020	-2.955	0.0331	-----	-----	-----	I(0)

Table 3: Zivot-Andrews(ZA) Unit Root Test Results

Variables	Level		First Difference		Remarks
	t-Statistics	5% critical value	t-statistics	5%-critical	
LGDP	-3.062	-4.50	-4.607	-4.50	I(1)
ITR	-3.796	-4.80	-8.719	-4.80	I(1)
TBR	-3.849	-4.80	-8.446	-4.80	I(1)
LRRR	-3.044	-4.80	-5.756	-4.80	I(1)
LEXR	-2.639	-4.80	-6.139	-4.80	I(1)
INF	-5.014	-4.80	-----	-----	I(0)

Sources: Researcher's computation from Stata 16

Both ADF and PP unit root test as presented in table 1 & 2, revealed that treasury bill rate (TBR) and inflation rate (INF) were stationary at level, whereas gross domestic product (GDP), interest rate (INT), exchange rate (EXR) and reserve requirement ratio (RRR) were stationary at first difference. However, in order to take accurate decision on the nature of integration among the variables of interest, Zivot-Andrews test of stationarity was applied which revealed in table 3 that only inflation rate (INF) was actually stationary at level whereas gross domestic product (GDP), open market operation proxied by treasury bill rate (TBR), interest rate (INT), exchange rate (EXR) and reserve requirement ratio (RRR) were stationary at first difference. This Zivot-Andrews (ZA) unit root test results actually confirms the existence of a mixed order of integration among the variables of the study, This mixed order of integration from the unit root test results implies the possibility of long-run relationship among the variables of the study, though further investigations using Estat Ectest-Bound test result will reveal if actually long run relationship exist among the variables of the study.

4.2 ARDL Bound Test

Table 4: Bound Test Result

Kripfganz and Schneider (2020) critical values and approximate p-values						F = 6.907
						t = -6.310
	10%		5%		1%	p-value
	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)
F	2.398	3.485	2.888	4.120	4.068	5.635
t	-2.516	-3.629	-2.875	-4.048	-3.608	-4.897
					0.000	0.003
					0.000	0.000

Sources: Researcher’s computation from Stata 16

Table 4 shows the existence of long-run relationship monetary policy instruments and economic growth in Nigeria within the periods of the study as computed *F* value of (6.907) is greater 4.120 upper critical value at 5% level of significance.

4.3 ARDL Short-Run Results

Table 5: ARDL Short-run Coefficients Test

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t-Statistic	Prob	95% Conf.	Interval
LGDP	-.4642958	.1115061	-4.16	0.001	-.7019654	-.2266262
ITR	-.0071859	.0031012	-2.32	0.035	-.0137959	-.0005759
TBR	.0174132	.004124	4.22	0.001	.0262033	-.0086231
LRRR	-.0686578	.0182017	-3.77	0.002	-.0298618	.1074538
LEXR	-.0941616	.031901	-2.95	0.010	-.162157	-.0261661
INF	-.0032274	.0006943	-4.65	0.000	-.0006943	.0047073

R² = 0.9760; Adj R² = 0.9409

Sources: Researcher’s computation from Stata 16

Table 5 illustrates the short-run coefficients test results of the ARDL model. The results indicated that interest rate (ITR), exchange rate (EXR) and inflation rate (INF) at lag 1, with the coefficient of -.0071859, -.0941616 and -.0032274 and p-value of 0.035, 0.010 and 0.000 have negative impact on GDP in Nigeria and as well, statistically significant in the short-run. Similarly, the coefficient of reserve requirement ratio (RESR) at lag 1 being -.0686578 with associate p-value of 0.002, implies negative association between reserve requirement ratio and GDP; and as well, statistically significant in the short-run in Nigeria. However, the coefficient of treasury bill rate (TBR) at lag 1 being 0.0174132 with associate p-value of 0.001, implies positive association between treasury bill rate and GDP; and as well, statistically significant in the short-run in Nigeria. The above result shows that the R² is 0.9760, which implies that the model explains about 97.60% of the total variations in GDP are explained by the independent variables during the period of the study.

4.4 Long Run Results

Table 6: ARDL Long-run Coefficients Test Results

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t-Statistic	Prob	95% Conf.	Interval
ECT	-.6595432	.2242561	-2.94	0.026	-1.208278	-.1108083
ITR	-1.063453	.4090206	-2.60	0.003	-1.244861	.7568136
TBR	1.063453	.4090206	2.60	0.003	1.244861	.7568136
LRRR	-1.15012	.9366977	-1.23	0.238	-3.146644	8464037
LEXR	-2.635483	1.191967	-2.21	0.043	.0948656	5.1761
INF	-.0413272	.0146193	-2.83	0.013	-.0101668	0724876
Cons	8.530587	1.56452	5.45	0.000	5.195891	11.86528

Sources: Researcher’s computation from Stata 16

Table 6 reveals the long-run coefficients test results of the ARDL model for which the variables under consideration were estimated. From the results, ECT value is -.6595432, and p-value being 0.026, shows significance at 5 percent critical value. It is also discovered in the result that interest rate (ITR),

exchange rate (EXR) and inflation rate (INF) with the coefficient of -1.063453, -.635483 and -.0413272 and p-value of 0.003, 0.043 and 0.013 have negative impact on gross domestic product in Nigeria and as well, statistically significant in the long-run. However, the coefficient of treasury bill rate (TBR) being 1.063453 with associate p-value of 0.003, implies positive association between treasury bill rate and gross domestic product; and as well, statistically significant in the long-run in Nigeria. On the contrary, the coefficient of reserve requirement ratio (LRRR) being -1.15012 with associate p-value of 0.238, implies negative association between reserve requirement ratio and gross domestic product; but statistically not significant in the long-run in Nigeria.

Table 7: Dynamic ARDL Results

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t-Statistic	Prob	95% Conf. Interval
LGDP @ Level	.0227512	.0369074	0.62	0.544	.0991001 .0535976
ITR @ Level	-.0089235	.0043874	-2.03	0.044	-.0179994 .0001525
TBR @ Level	.4307308	.163776	2.63	0.011	.0775363 .6106247
LRRR @ lag 1	-.0263046	.0241022	-1.09	0.286	-.0235545 .0761638
LEXR @ Lag 1	-.0939948	.0429684	-2.19	0.039	.0051079 .1828816
INF	-.0023664	.0010612	-2.23	0.036	.000171 .0045617
C	.2032112	.2171805	0.94	0.359	-.2460609 .6524834

R² = 0.8784; Adj R² = 0.7937

Table 7 illustrates the test results of the Dynamic ARDL model. The results indicated that when monetary policy instruments are held constant, the gross domestic product (LGDP) only increases by 0.23%. But with 1% increase in interest rate (ITR), gross domestic product (LGDP) decreases by 0.01%. This result is statistically significant as its probability value is 0.044. In the same vein, with 1% increase in both exchange rate (LEXR) and inflation rate (INF), gross domestic product (LGDP) decreases by 0.09% and 0.002% respectively. These results are statistically significant as their probability values are 0.039 and 0.036 respectively. However, 1% increase in treasury bill rate (TBR), increases gross domestic product (LGDP) by 0.43%. This result is statistically significant as its probability value is 0.011. In the same vein, 1% increase in reserve requirement ratio (LRRR), increases gross domestic product (LGDP) by 0.03%. This result is statistically not significant as its probability values 0.286. The above result shows that R² being 0.8784, implies that the model explains about 87.84% of the total variations in gross domestic product (LGDP) are explained by the independent variables (interest rate, exchange rate, treasury bill rate, reserve requirement ratio and inflation rate) during the period of the study. While the remaining 12.16% variations are as a result of other explanatory variables that are not captured in the model.

Figure 1: Impulse Response Analysis with respect to LEXR

The figure 2 showed that a one standard deviation shocks LEXR initially has no noticeable impact on LGDP from periods 1 to 9. However, from period 10, the response maintained a slight decreases till the 11th periods after which it maintained a steady state. Hence, there there was a shock from LEXR to LGDP and after which, a steady state was maintained. This result indicates that shocks to exchange rate (LEXR) will have asymmetric impact on gross domestic product (LGDP) in both the short-run and the long-run in Nigeria.

4.5 Diagnostic Tests

The diagnostic test is employed to validate the ARDL model results in which the serial correlation, heteroscedasticity and error specifications were tested for stability through the applications of the B-Godfrey serial correlation and ARCHLM heteroskedasticity Test. These diagnostic tests were utilized to determine whether the parameters of the model possessed goodness of fit for the investigation as suggested by Pesaran and Pesaran (1997). The results are presented in the table 7 below:

Table 8: Post Estimation Test Results

Test	chi ²	DF	p-value
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	0.637	1	0.4249
Heteroskedasticity Test	0.200	1	0.6549

Sources: Researcher’s computation STATA 16

The post-diagnostic result in table 7 above revealed that there is no presence of serial correlation and Heteroskedasticity as their respective probability and chi square value of F-statistic are more than 5% level of significance.

Figure 2: Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) of Square Test

The cumulative sum (CUSUM) of residuals test is employed to unveil the structural changes in the coefficient of the regression model, whereas the cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMSQ) test for sudden changes in the constancy of the regression equations. From Figure 3, the results showed stability in the parameters of the equations at the CUSUMSQ as its plot fell within the critical bands at a 5% level of significance.

4.6 Test of Research Hypotheses

Decision Rule: If the chosen level of significance (0.05) at 5% level of significance is greater than the p-value, the null hypothesis is rejected, otherwise, will not be rejected. This is applicable to all the hypotheses in this research work.

4.6.1 Hypothesis One

There is no significant impact between interest rate and economic growth in Nigeria.

From tables 5 and 7 in section four, the coefficients of interest rate in short and long run are -0.007 and -0.0089235 respectively and its respective p-values are 0.035 and 0.044. The p-value of the parameter is statistically significant at 5 percent critical value. Since the coefficient of the estimated variable is negative and its p-value is statistically significant, the null hypothesis is rejected and the study concludes that interest rate has a negative and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria in both short run and long run.

4.6.2 Hypothesis Two

There is no significant impact between exchange rate and economic growth in Nigeria.

From tables 5 and 7 in section four, the coefficients of exchange rate in short and long run are -0.094 and -0.093 respectively and its p-values are 0.010 and 0.039 respectively. The p-value of the parameter is statistically significant at 5 percent critical value. Since the coefficient of the estimated variable is negative and its p-value is statistically significant, the null hypothesis is rejected and the study concludes that exchange rate has a negative and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria in the long run.

4.6.3 Hypothesis Three

Open market operation has no significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

From tables 5 and 7 in section four, the coefficients of treasury bill rates as a proxy for open market operation in short and long run are 0.017 and 0.4307308 respectively and its p-values are 0.001 and 0.011 respectively. The p-value of the parameter is statistically significant at 5 percent critical value. Since the coefficient of the estimated variable is positive and its p-value is statistically significant, the

null hypothesis is rejected and the study concludes that open market operation has a positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria both in the short run and long run.

4.6.4 Hypothesis Four

Reserve requirement ratio has no significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

From tables 5 and 7 in section four, the coefficients of reserve requirement ratio in short and long run are -0.068 and -0.026 respectively and its p-values are 0.002 and 0.286 respectively. The p-value of the parameter is statistically not significant at 5 percent critical value in the long run. Since the coefficient of the estimated variable is negative and its p-value is statistically not significant in the long run, the null hypothesis is rejected and the study concludes that reserve requirement ratio has a negative and insignificant impact on economic growth in Nigeria in the long run, but does in the short run.

DISCUSSION

5.1 Extent of Impact of Interest Rate on Economic Growth in Nigeria

In effort to attain this objective, the results estimated using the Dynamic ARDL model was utilized to examine the significant effect of interest rate on economic growth in Nigeria. From the result, the coefficient of interest rate is -0.0089235 and its p-value is 0.044. These results show that interest rate at 5 percent critical value has a negative and significant effect on economic growth. Thus, the study estimated on the average that 1% increase in interest rate resulted to 0.009% decrease in economic growth in Nigeria. The above results are in line with classical theory of money which maintains that a higher interest rate negatively impacts economic growth by discouraging investment as businesses are less likely to borrow money at a higher cost. Empirically, the results are in accordance with the discoveries of Gediyon (2021), Senzeni (2019), Lubo and Bigbo (2021), Ying, Yunpeng and Mengya (2021), etc, who noted that interest rate negatively impacts on economic growth in the country. The implication of this result is that interest rate had been discouraging investment which is synonymous with economic growth in the country. However, the findings contradict the results of Sesay and Abdulai (2017), Thuy, Anh and Diem (2020), etc reported positive impact of interest rate on economic growth.

5.2 Extent of Impact of Exchange Rate on Economic Growth in Nigeria

In effort to attain this objective, the results estimated using the Dynamic ARDL model was utilized to examine the significant effect of exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria. From the result, the coefficient of exchange rate is -0.0939948 and its p-value is 0.039. These results show that exchange rate at 5 percent critical value has a negative and significant effect on economic growth. Thus, the study estimated on the average that 1% increase in exchange rate resulted to 0.09% decrease in economic growth in Nigeria. The above results are in line with classical theory of money which maintains that exchange rate fluctuations have minimal negative impact on long-term economic growth. Empirically, the results are in accordance with the discoveries of Mbanasor and Obioma (2017), Hiluf and Naser (2021) and Bakare (2011), etc who noted that exchange rate negatively impacts on economic growth in the country. The implication of this result is that exchange rate had been discouraging investment which is synonymous with economic growth in the country. However, the findings contradict the results of but also in disagreement with the work done by Paulo Gala and Marcos Rocha (2015) and Bilge and Gozde (2017), etc, to mention, but a few that reported positive impact of exchange rate on economic growth.

5.3 Extent of Impact of Open Market Operation on Economic Growth in Nigeria

In effort to attain this objective, the results estimated using the Dynamic ARDL model was utilized to examine the significant effect of open market operation on economic growth in Nigeria. From the result, the coefficient of treasury bill rate as proxy for open market operation is 0.4307308 and its p-value is 0.011. These results show that open market operation at 5 percent critical value has a positive and significant effect on economic growth. Thus, the study estimated on the average that 1% increase in open market operation resulted to 0.43% increase in economic growth in Nigeria. The above results are in line with classical theory of money which maintains that open market operation affects economic growth by directly influencing the money supply through buying or selling government securities, where buying securities injects money into the economy thereby stimulating the economic growth. Empirically, the results are in accordance with the discovery Awogbemi (2022), Okoh &

Otene (2020), etc who noted that open market operation positively impacts on economic growth in the country. The implication of this result is that open market operation had been encouraging investment which is synonymous with economic growth in the country. However, the findings are also in disagreement with the work done by Ofonime, Ubong and Idongesit, (2022) and Addoi and Sunzuoye (2013), etc.

5.4 Extent of Impact of Reserve Requirement Ratio on Economic Growth in Nigeria

In effort to attain this objective, the results estimated using the Dynamic ARDL model was utilized to examine the significant effect of reserve requirement ratio on economic growth in Nigeria. From the result, the coefficient of reserve requirement ratio is -0.0263046 and its p-value is 0.286. These results show that reserve requirement ratio at 5 percent critical value has a negative and insignificant effect on economic growth. Thus, the study estimated on the average that 1% increase in reserve requirement ratio resulted to 0.03% decrease in economic growth in Nigeria. The above results are in line with Keynesian monetary theory which maintained that a higher reserve requirement ratio generally leads to a decrease in economic growth by limiting the amount of money banks can lend out, which reduces the money supply and restricts credit availability, thereby hindering investment and overall economic activity. Empirically, the results are in accordance with the discovery of Fatima and Samreen, (2015) and Bawa, Akinniyi and Njarendy (2018), etc who noted that reserve requirement ratio negatively impacts on economic growth in the country. The implication of this result is that open market operation had been discouraging investment which is synonymous with economic growth in the country. However, the findings are also in disagreement with the work done by Tevy (2021), etc.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Summary of Findings

The study investigated the impact of monetary policy instruments on economic growth in Nigeria for the period of 1981 to 2022. Using Dynamic Autoregressive Distributed lag (ARDL) model, we discovered that: A percentage increase in interest rate in the short and long run brought about 0.007% and 0.009% decrease in economic growth in Nigeria respectively. The negative relationship between interest rate and economic growth in Nigeria is in line with the a priori expectation. It simply means that a higher interest rate discourages investment as businesses are less likely to borrow money at a higher cost, while simultaneously encouraging savings, which can limit the available funds for investment. Again, one percentage increase in open market operation proxied by treasury bill rate in the country brought about an approximately 0.02% and 0.43% increase in economic growth in Nigeria respectively in the short and long run periods. It implies that increase in treasury bill rate conducted by a central bank by buying government securities, have a direct impact on economic growth by influencing the money supply by allowing it to stimulate growth during economic downturns.

Furthermore, one percentage increase in reserve requirement ratio brought about 0.07% and 0.03% decrease in economic growth in Nigeria respectively in the short and long run periods. This result implies that the reserve requirement ratio and economic growth are negatively related. It simply means that a higher reserve requirement ratio generally has a negative relationship with economic growth, as it restricts the amount of money banks can lend out, thereby limiting credit availability and potentially slowing down economic activity.

Again, one percentage increase in exchange rate brought about 0.094% 0.09% decrease in economic growth in Nigeria in the short and long run periods respectively. This result implies that the exchange rate and economic growth are negatively related. It simply means that an appreciating exchange rate can negatively affect growth by discouraging exports and encouraging imports. Lastly, one percentage increase in inflation rate in the short and long run brought about 0.003% and 0.002% decrease in economic growth in Nigeria respectively. This result implies that the inflation rate and economic growth are negatively related. It simply means that high interest rates can dampen economic growth by making borrowing more expensive and discouraging investment.

6.2 CONCLUSION

The study examined the effect of monetary policy instruments on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1981-2022. Dynamic Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model is the method of analysis

utilized in the investigation. The variables modeled in the research include gross domestic product (GDP-dependent variable) and the independent variables include interest rate (ITR), exchange rate (EXR), open market operation proxied by treasury bill rate (TBR), reserve requirement ratio (RRR) and inflation rate (INF). The employed variables have different order of integration ranging from zero and one, which led to the application of Dynamic ARDL. The results of the E-stat and Bound Test revealed the presence of equilibrium long-run relationship among the variables used in the model. The results estimated indicated that both interest rate, exchange rate and inflation rate have negative and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. The results also showed that reserve requirement ratio exerted negative impact on economic growth and also statistically significant in the short-run but in the long-run, it has negative and insignificant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. On the contrary, open market operation proxied by treasury bill rate impacted positively and statistically significant on economic growth in Nigeria. Based on the results of the study highlighted above, the study concludes that monetary policy instruments are very good measure towards the improving the economy of a country.

6.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1). Since interest rate negatively and significantly impacts on economic growth in Nigeria, government should liberalize interest rate such that will reduce prime lending rate and thereby encourage investors to access the credit available domestic investment in Nigeria.
- 2). As exchange rate negatively and significantly impacts on economic growth in Nigeria, the monetary authorities should formulate policy that would strengthen exchange rate so that it stimulate economic growth through investment in Nigeria.
- 3). Having found that open market operation proxied by treasury bill positively and significantly impacts on economic growth in Nigeria, the monetary authority should use descriptive monetary policy to formulate policies that would increase treasury bill so as to improve economic growth
- 4). Since reserve requirement ratio negatively and insignificantly impacts on economic growth in Nigeria, Government should embark on policies that would increase the commercial bank reserve as that would increase the availability of fund to the investor for investment and in turn promote private domestic investment.

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APPENDICES

Year	GDP	ITR	TBR	RRR	EXR	INF	
1981	139.31	6.5		5	0	0.6231	20.81
1982	149.05	8		7	0	0.6729	7.7
1983	158.75	8		7	0	0.7241	23.21
1984	165.85	10		8.5	0	0.7649	17.82
1985	187.83	10		8.5	0	0.8938	7.44
1986	198.12	10		8.5	0	2.0206	5.72
1987	244.68	15.8		11.75	0	4.0179	11.29
1988	315.62	14.3		11.75	0	4.5367	54.51
1989	414.86	21.2		17.5	0	7.3916	50.47
1990	494.64	23		17.5	0	8.0378	7.36
1991	590.06	20.1		15	0	9.9095	13.01
1992	906.03	20.5		21	3.35	17.2984	44.59
1993	1,257.17	28.02		26.9	6.74	22.0511	57.17
1994	1,768.79	15		12.5	8.41	21.8861	57.03
1995	3,100.24	14.27		12.5	10.86	21.8861	72.84
1996	4,086.07	13.55		12.25	16.95	21.8861	29.27

1997	4,418.71	7.43	12	22.74	21.8861	8.53
1998	4,805.16	10.09	12.95	27.74	21.8861	10
1999	5,482.35	14.3	17	62	92.6934	6.62
2000	7,062.75	10.44	12	77.78	102.1052	6.93
2001	8,234.49	10.09	12.95	125.26	111.9433	18.87
2002	11,501.45	15.57	18.88	139.7	120.9702	12.88
2003	13,556.97	11.88	15.02	152.28	129.3565	14.03
2004	18,124.06	12.21	14.21	157.96	133.5004	15
2005	23,121.88	8.68	7	101.1	132.147	17.86
2006	30,375.18	8.26	8.8	206.51	128.6516	8.23
2007	34,675.94	9.49	6.91	148.1	125.8331	5.39
2008	39,954.21	11.95	9.55	150.71	118.5669	11.58
2009	43,461.46	12.63	1.3	87.03	148.8802	12.56
2010	55,469.35	7.19	10.25	95.65	150.298	13.72
2011	63,713.36	6.3	16.75	770.05	153.8616	10.84
2012	72,599.63	7.63	17.2	1,338.80	157.4994	12.22
2013	81,009.96	6.72	13.34	2,270.44	157.3112	8.48
2014	90,136.98	9.89	15.99	3,578.54	158.5526	8.06
2015	95,177.74	8.26	16.28	3,086.00	193.2792	9.01
2016	102,575.42	5.46	18.5	3,439.99	198.2515	15.68
2017	114,899.25	7.73	18.98	3,944.10	198.5621	16.52
2018	129,086.91	8.85	14.55	3692.04688	200.0212	12.09
2019	145,639.14	8.46	15	3818.074653	202.3252	11.4
2020	154,252.32	13.5	6.31	3755.060767	358.8321	13.25
2021	176,075.50	11.5	10	3786.56771	457.6432	16.95
2022	202,365.03	16.5	10.44	3786.56	448	18.85

dfuller lgdp, lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 41

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-1.455	-3.641	-2.955
			-2.611

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.5557

dfuller d.lgdp, lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 40

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-3.500	-3.648	-2.958
			-2.612

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0080

dfuller itr , lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 41

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-2.767	-3.641	-2.611

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0632

dfuller d.itr , lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 40

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-7.340	-3.648	-2.612

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0000

dfuller tbr , lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 41

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-3.489	-3.641	-2.611

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0083

dfuller lrrr , lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 41

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-0.378	-3.641	-2.611

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.9137

dfuller d.lrrr , lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 40

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-5.202	-3.648	-2.612

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0000

dfuller lexr , lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 41

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-2.052	-3.641	-2.611

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.2641
dfuller d.lexr , lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 40

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-5.470	-3.648	-2.612

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0000

dfuller inf , lags(0)

Dickey-Fuller test for unit root Number of obs = 41

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(t)	-3.050	-3.641	-2.611

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0304

pperron lgdp

Phillips-Perron test for unit root Number of obs = 41
Newey-West lags = 3

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(rho)	-0.478	-18.288	-10.520
Z(t)	-1.111	-3.641	-2.611

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.7107

pperron d.lgdp

Phillips-Perron test for unit root Number of obs = 40
Newey-West lags = 3

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(rho)	-18.578	-18.220	-10.500
Z(t)	-3.469	-3.648	-2.612

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(rho)	-33.299	-18.220	-12.980
Z(t)	-5.203	-3.648	-2.958

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0000

pperron lexr

Phillips-Perron test for unit root Number of obs = 41
Newey-West lags = 3

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(rho)	-1.861	-18.288	-13.012
Z(t)	-2.101	-3.641	-2.955

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.2441

pperron d.lexr

Phillips-Perron test for unit root Number of obs = 40
Newey-West lags = 3

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(rho)	-34.817	-18.220	-12.980
Z(t)	-5.458	-3.648	-2.958

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0000

pperron inf

Phillips-Perron test for unit root Number of obs = 41
Newey-West lags = 3

----- Interpolated Dickey-Fuller -----

Test	1% Critical	5% Critical	10% Critical
Statistic	Value	Value	Value
Z(rho)	-15.403	-18.288	-13.012
Z(t)	-3.020	-3.641	-2.955

Mackinnon approximate p-value for Z(t) = 0.0331

. zandrews lgdp

Zivot-Andrews unit root test for lgdp

Allowing for break in intercept

Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.lgdp included = 1

Minimum t-statistic -3.062 at 1992 (obs 12)

Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.50 10%: -4.58

. zandrews d.lgdp

Zivot-Andrews unit root test for D.lgdp

Allowing for break in intercept

Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.D.lgdp included = 0

Minimum t-statistic -4.607 at 1988 (obs 8)

Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.50 10%: -4.58

. zandrews itr
Zivot-Andrews unit root test for itr
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.itr included = 2
Minimum t-statistic -3.796 at 1989 (obs 9)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

zandrews d.itr
Zivot-Andrews unit root test for D.itr
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.D.itr included = 1
Minimum t-statistic -8.719 at 1994 (obs 14)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

zandrews tbr
Zivot-Andrews unit root test for tbr
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.tbr included = 0
Minimum t-statistic -3.849 at 1987 (obs 7)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

.Zivot-Andrews unit root test for D.tbr
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.D.tbr included = 0
Minimum t-statistic -8.446 at 1994 (obs 14)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

zandrews lrrr
Zivot-Andrews unit root test for lrrr
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.lrrr included = 1
Minimum t-statistic -3.044 at 1995 (obs 15)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

zandrews d.lrrr
Zivot-Andrews unit root test for D.lrrr
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.D.lrrr included = 0
Minimum t-statistic -5.756 at 1992 (obs 12)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

zandrews lexr
Zivot-Andrews unit root test for lexr
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.lexr included = 0
Minimum t-statistic -2.639 at 1987 (obs 7)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

zandrews d.lexr
Zivot-Andrews unit root test for D.lexr
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.D.lexr included = 0
Minimum t-statistic -6.139 at 2001 (obs 21)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

zandrews inf
Zivot-Andrews unit root test for inf
Allowing for break in intercept
Lag selection via TTest: lags of D.inf included = 1
Minimum t-statistic -5.014 at 1999 (obs 19)
Critical values: 1%: -5.34 5%: -4.80 10%: -4.58

```
. varsoc lgdp itr tbr lrrr lexr inf
Selection-order criteria
Sample: 1985 - 2022          Number of obs   =    38
-----+-----+
|lag| LL   LR   df  p   FPE   AIC   HQIC   SBIC |
-----+-----+
| 0 | -495.945          11980 26.4182 26.5102 26.6767 |
| 1 | -290.062 411.77 36 0.000 1.60835 17.4769 18.1209 19.2869* |
| 2 | -243.389 93.345 36 0.000 1.06227 16.9152 18.1112 20.2766 |
| 3 | -190.651 105.48 36 0.000 .669443 16.0343 17.7822 20.947 |
| 4 | -132.557 116.19* 36 0.000 .559065* 14.8714* 17.1713* 21.3356 |
-----+-----+
```

```
Endogenous: lgdp itr tbr lrrr lexr inf
Exogenous: _cons
. ardl lgdp itr tbr lrrr lexr inf, ec1 restricted maxlags(4)aic
ARDL(4,1,3,3,3,3) regression
Sample: 1985 - 2022          Number of obs   =    38
                               R-squared         =    0.9760
                               Adj R-squared      =    0.9409
Log likelihood = 100.71184          Root MSE      =    0.0272
```

D.lgdp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
ADJ						
lgdp						
L1.	-.6595432	.2242561	-2.940	0.026	-1.208278	-.1108083
LR						
itr						
L1.	-1.063453	.4090206	-2.60	0.003	-1.244861	.7568136
tbr						
L1.	1.063453	.4090206	2.60	0.003	1.244861	.7568136
lrrr						
L1.	-1.15012	.9366977	-1.23	0.238	-3.146644	.8464037
lexr						
L1.	-2.635483	1.191967	-2.21	0.043	-.0948656	5.1761
inf						
L1.	-.0413272	.0146193	-2.83	0.013	-.0101668	.0724876
_cons	8.530587	1.56452	5.45	0.000	5.195891	11.86528

SR						
lgdp						
LD.	-.4642958	.1115061	-4.16	0.001	-.7019654	-.2266262
L2D.	-.0934779	.1094264	-0.85	0.406	-.3267148	.139759
L3D.	-.255294	.1093185	-2.34	0.034	-.4883007	-.0222872
itr						
D1.	-.0071859	.0031012	-2.32	0.035	-.0137959	-.0005759
tbr						
D1.	.0021092	.0027749	0.76	0.459	-.0038053	.0080237
LD.	.0174132	.004124	4.22	0.001	.0262033	-.0086231
L2D.	-.0118707	.0032181	-3.69	0.002	-.01873	-.0050114
lrrr						
D1.	.0100025	.0214921	0.47	0.648	-.0358067	.0558118
LD.	-.0686578	.0182017	-3.77	0.002	-.0298618	.1074538
L2D.	.032644	.0174392	1.87	0.081	-.0045268	.0698148
lexr						
D1.	-.0245581	.0223645	-1.10	0.289	-.072227	.0231108

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs =	40
				F(16, 23)	= 10.38
Model	.436575095	16	.027285943	Prob > F	= 0.0000
Residual	.060459638	23	.00262868	R-squared	= 0.8784
				Adj R-squared	= 0.7937
Total	.497034732	39	.01274448	Root MSE	= .05127

dlgdp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
L1_lgdp	.0227512	.0369074	0.62	0.544	.0991001 .0535976
D_itr	-.0089235	.0043874	-2.03	0.044	-.0179994 .0001525
L1_itr	-.0064036	.0089391	-0.72	0.481	-.0248955 .0120882
L1D_itr	-.005255	.0051817	-1.01	0.321	-.0159741 .0054641
D_tbr	.4307308	.163776	2.63	0.011	.0775363 .6106247
D_lrrr	-.0045723	.0286914	-0.16	0.875	-.0639249 .0547803
D_lexr	.0047815	.0385186	0.12	0.902	-.0749003 .0844633
D_inf	.0011311	.0009693	1.17	0.255	-.0008741 .0031363
L1_tbr	.0099896	.0069161	1.44	0.162	-.0043175 .0242967
L1_lrrr	-.0518677	.0278847	-1.86	0.076	-.1095517 .0058162
L1_lexr	-.0939948	.0429684	-2.19	0.039	-.0051079 .1828816
L1_inf	-.0022383	.0605061	-0.04	0.971	-.126853 .1223765
L1D_tbr	-.0103191	.0037465	-2.75	0.011	-.0180692 -.0025689
L1D_lrrr	.0263046	.0241022	1.09	0.286	-.0235545 .0761638
L1D_lexr	.0411676	.0435255	0.95	0.354	-.0488717 .1312069
L1D_inf	-.0023664	.0010612	-2.23	0.036	.000171 .0045617
_cons	.2032112	.2171805	0.94	0.359	-.2460609 .6524834

Please wait:
 dynardl is currently creating 500 simulations across 30 time points (30)
 ----- 1 ----- 2 ----- 3 ----- 4 ----- 5
 50
 file dynardl_results.dta saved


```
dynardl lgdp itr tbr lrrr lexr inf, lags(1,1,1,1,1) diffs(.,1,1,1,1,1) lagdiffs(.,1,1,1,1,1) shockvar(tbr) ec
> shockval(-1) time(10) range(30) graph sims(500)
```

Option ec specified, dependent variable to be run in differences

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs =	40
--------	----	----	----	-----------------	----

```
-----+----- F(16, 23) = 10.38
Model | .436575095 16 .027285943 Prob > F = 0.0000
Residual | .060459638 23 .00262868 R-squared = 0.8784
-----+----- Adj R-squared = 0.7937
Total | .497034732 39 .01274448 Root MSE = .05127
```

```
-----+-----
dlgdp | Coef. Std. Err. t P>|t| [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
L1_lgdp | -.0227512 .0369074 -0.62 0.544 -.0991001 .0535976
D_tbr | .0051832 .0034552 1.50 0.147 -.0019646 .0123309
L1_tbr | .0099896 .0069161 1.44 0.162 -.0043175 .0242967
L1D_tbr | -.0103191 .0037465 -2.75 0.011 -.0180692 -.0025689
D_itr | -.0089235 .0043874 -2.03 0.054 -.0179994 .0001525
D_lrrr | -.0045723 .0286914 -0.16 0.875 -.0639249 .0547803
D_lexr | .0047815 .0385186 0.12 0.902 -.0749003 .0844633
D_inf | .0011311 .0009693 1.17 0.255 -.0008741 .0031363
L1_itr | -.0064036 .0089391 -0.72 0.481 -.0248955 .0120882
L1_lrrr | -.0518677 .0278847 -1.86 0.076 -.1095517 .0058162
L1_lexr | .0939948 .0429684 2.19 0.039 .0051079 .1828816
L1_inf | .0010528 .0013171 0.80 0.432 -.0016718 .0037774
L1D_itr | -.005255 .0051817 -1.01 0.321 -.0159741 .0054641
L1D_lrrr | -.0263046 .0241022 -1.09 0.286 -.0235545 .0761638
L1D_lexr | .0411676 .0435255 0.95 0.354 -.0488717 .1312069
L1D_inf | .0023664 .0010612 2.23 0.036 .000171 .0045617
_cons | .2032112 .2171805 0.94 0.359 -.2460609 .6524834
-----+-----
```

Please wait:
 dynardl is currently creating 500 simulations across 30 time points (30)
 -----+----- 1 -----+----- 2 -----+----- 3 -----+----- 4 -----+----- 5
 50
 file dynardl_results.dta saved


```
dynardl lgdp itr tbr lrrr lexr inf, lags(1,1,1,1,1,1) diffs(.,1,1,1,1,1) lagdiffs(.,1,1,1,1,1) shockvar(lrrr) ec
> shockval(-1) time(10) range(30) graph sims(500)
```

Option ec specified, dependent variable to be run in differences

```
-----+-----
Source | SS df MS Number of obs = 40
-----+----- F(16, 23) = 10.38
```

```

Model | .436575095    16 .027285943 Prob > F    = 0.0000
Residual | .060459638    23 .00262868 R-squared    = 0.8784
-----+----- Adj R-squared = 0.7937
Total | .497034732    39 .01274448 Root MSE    = .05127
    
```

dlgdp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
L1_lgdp	-.0227512	.0369074	-0.62	0.544	-.0991001 .0535976
D_lrrr	-.0045723	.0286914	-0.16	0.875	-.0639249 .0547803
L1_lrrr	-.0518677	.0278847	-1.86	0.076	-.1095517 .0058162
L1D_lrrr	.0263046	.0241022	1.09	0.286	-.0235545 .0761638
D_itr	-.0089235	.0043874	-2.03	0.054	-.0179994 .0001525
D_tbr	.0051832	.0034552	1.50	0.147	-.0019646 .0123309
D_lexr	.0047815	.0385186	0.12	0.902	-.0749003 .0844633
D_inf	.0011311	.0009693	1.17	0.255	-.0008741 .0031363
L1_itr	-.0064036	.0089391	-0.72	0.481	-.0248955 .0120882
L1_tbr	.0099896	.0069161	1.44	0.162	-.0043175 .0242967
L1_lexr	.0939948	.0429684	2.19	0.039	.0051079 .1828816
L1_inf	.0010528	.0013171	0.80	0.432	-.0016718 .0037774
L1D_itr	-.005255	.0051817	-1.01	0.321	-.0159741 .0054641
L1D_tbr	-.0103191	.0037465	-2.75	0.011	-.0180692 -.0025689
L1D_lexr	.0411676	.0435255	0.95	0.354	-.0488717 .1312069
L1D_inf	.0023664	.0010612	2.23	0.036	.000171 .0045617
_cons	.2032112	.2171805	0.94	0.359	-.2460609 .6524834

```

Please wait:
dynardl is currently creating 500 simulations across 30 time points (30)
----- 1 ---- 2 ---- 3 ---- 4 ---- 5
..... 50
file dynardl_results.dta saved
    
```



```

dynardl lgdp itr tbr lrrr lexr inf, lags(1,1,1,1,1) diffs(.,1,1,1,1) lagdiffs(.,1,1,1,1) shockvar(lexr) ec
> shockval(-1) time(10) range(30) graph sims(500)
    
```

Option ec specified, dependent variable to be run in differences

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs =	40
----- F(16, 23) = 10.38					
Model	.436575095	16	.027285943	Prob > F	= 0.0000
Residual	.060459638	23	.00262868	R-squared	= 0.8784
----- Adj R-squared = 0.7937					
Total	.497034732	39	.01274448	Root MSE	= .05127

dlgdp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
L1_lgdp	-.0227512	.0369074	-0.62	0.544	-.0991001	.0535976
D_lexr	.0047815	.0385186	0.12	0.902	-.0749003	.0844633
L1_lexr	.0939948	.0429684	2.19	0.039	.0051079	.1828816
L1D_lexr	.0411676	.0435255	0.95	0.354	-.0488717	.1312069
D_itr	-.0089235	.0043874	-2.03	0.054	-.0179994	.0001525
D_tbr	.0051832	.0034552	1.50	0.147	-.0019646	.0123309
D_lrrr	-.0045723	.0286914	-0.16	0.875	-.0639249	.0547803
D_inf	.0011311	.0009693	1.17	0.255	-.0008741	.0031363
L1_itr	-.0064036	.0089391	-0.72	0.481	-.0248955	.0120882
L1_tbr	.0099896	.0069161	1.44	0.162	-.0043175	.0242967
L1_lrrr	-.0518677	.0278847	-1.86	0.076	-.1095517	.0058162
L1_inf	.0010528	.0013171	0.80	0.432	-.0016718	.0037774
L1D_itr	-.005255	.0051817	-1.01	0.321	-.0159741	.0054641
L1D_tbr	-.0103191	.0037465	-2.75	0.011	-.0180692	-.0025689
L1D_lrrr	.0263046	.0241022	1.09	0.286	-.0235545	.0761638
L1D_inf	.0023664	.0010612	2.23	0.036	.000171	.0045617
_cons	.2032112	.2171805	0.94	0.359	-.2460609	.6524834

Please wait:
 dynardl is currently creating 500 simulations across 30 time points (30)
 ----- 1 ----- 2 ----- 3 ----- 4 ----- 5
 50
 file dynardl_results.dta saved

